

Supplementary Material

Long-term in-vitro Recording of Cardiac Action Potentials on Microelectrode Arrays for Chronic Cardiotoxicity Assessment

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S1. Live/Dead assay after repeated optoporation

Fig. S1: Live/Dead assay of cardiomyocytes on 6-well MEA (60-6wellMEA200/30iR-Ti-rcr) imaged with an inverted microscope (20X). Live cells are stained with green fluorescence (Calcein AM), whereas dead cells with red fluorescence (Ethidium homodimer-1). The uniform syncytium of cardiomyocytes labeled with calcein AM confirms that the cells are healthy after 6 repeated optoporation procedures. Scale bar: 30 μm .

S2. Control with dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)

Fig. S2: Long-term effect of DMSO on hiPSC-CMs. (a) Intracellular action potential waveforms before (control) and after administration of DMSO on iCell cardiomyocytes. (b) Action potential duration (APD30, 50, 90) without DMSO (control). (c, d) Action potential duration (APD30, 50, 90) after the administration of the amount of DMSO used for 1.5 μ M pentamidine and 10 nM doxorubicin administration, respectively. Data show that the administration of DMSO at tested concentration has no effect on the action potentials recorded with laser optoacoustic poration. Data are represented as mean \pm SEM of 3 wells.

S3. Effects of drugs detachable using optoporation

Fig. S3: (a) Early afterdepolarization (EADs) after 0.5 μM and 1.5 μM pentamidine administration, respectively. (b) Action potential shape variation and triangulation (e.g. after verapamil administration).

S4. Long-term effect of pentamidine

Fig. S4: Data analysis of long-term effect of pentamidine on hiPSC-CMs expressed as percentage of variation respect to control (100%). (a, b) Action potential duration at 90% of repolarization (APD90) after 0.5 μM and 1.5 μM pentamidine administration, respectively. Values are generated from the experiments showed in Fig. 4 and are represented as mean \pm SD of 3 wells.

S5. Repeated drugs exposures in Cor.4U cardiomyocytes

Fig. S5: Effects of dofetilide and nifedipine repeated administration on Cor.4U cardiomyocytes. (a, c) Action potential mean waveforms at different DIVs after administration of dofetilide (100 nM) and nifedipine (60 nM), respectively. (b, d) Action potential duration (APD50, 90) after dofetilide and nifedipine administration, respectively. Data are represented as mean \pm SEM of 3 wells.

S6. Long-term effect of doxorubicin

Fig. S6: Data analysis of long-term effect of doxorubicin on hiPSC-CMs expressed as percentage of variation respect to control (100%). (a, b) Action potential duration at 90% of repolarization (APD90) after 5 nM and 10 nM doxorubicin administration, respectively. Values are generated from the experiments showed in Fig. 5 and are represented as mean \pm SD of 3 wells.

S7. Data distribution in control condition

Fig: S7: Box plot of the action potential duration at 50% of the amplitude (APD50) in long-term measurements. The box plot graph shows the distribution of the data of APD50 for each day of measurement for the well of control reported in Fig. 2b.